

Examination Application Form

Before completing the application form, please ensure you comply with the eligibility criteria in section 2.2 of the Examination Procedures.

This form must be completed in BLOCK LETTERS throughout. It should be returned to ARB, together with all the supplementary material listed at Item 10: checklist, and the application fee, which is non-refundable in the event of cancellation. Postponed interviews will also attract additional administration fees.

Forms that are not completed properly will be returned to the applicant, as will forms that are not supported by the requisite supplementary material. Applicants will be charged a scrutiny fee of 25% if ARB must return their form. At the Board's discretion, additional fees may apply where incomplete applications are resubmitted.

Use this form if you have gained a qualification in architecture which ARB does not prescribe.

Have you read and understood ARB's guidance for applicants? Please take time to read it carefully before making your application.

Please specify which examination you're applying for:

Part 1

Part 2

Please note you must have secured Part 1 before applying for Part 2 examination.

Please attach passport size photo here

1. Personal details

Surname:

Forename/s:

Title (Mr, Mrs, Miss, Ms, Other):

Date of birth:

Nationality:

2. Corresponding details

Address:

Postcode:

Country:

Town:

County/State:

Telephone no:

Work
telephone no:

Email:

3. Previous assesment or examination details

Have you previously been examined by ARB?

Yes

No

Date of previous examination

Your reference number as detailed on ARB
letter/s:

4. Educational qualifications

Qualifications in architecture (in order of award, to end with most recent)

Name of school/college/university:

Full title of academic qualification:

Start date:

Date of award:

Country:

4. Educational qualifications I Continued

Name of school/college/university:

Full title of academic qualification:

Start date:

Date of award:

Country:

Name of school/college/university:

Full title of academic qualification:

Start date:

Date of award:

Country:

Name of school/college/university:

Full title of academic qualification:

Start date:

Date of award:

Country:

5. Evidence of identity

Please enclose a photocopy of your passport.

The passport must be brought to your examination for inspection.

6. References

Details of references supplied to support your application, if applicable.

You must provide the Board with appropriate references if you intend to present office-based or professional work in your Supporting Material.

(Please refer to the examination process document called Reference Templates)

I confirm that I am not relying on office based or professional work and no references are supplied.

I am presenting office-based or professional work and the following references are provided (please list).

7. English language ability

If English is not your first language, you must hold a valid IELTS (International English Language Testing System) certificate.*

This must be a single certificate at the academic level with no minimum band score below 6.5.

English is my first/dual language

I enclose a valid IELTS certificate*

*Please note, we only accept IELTS certificates

I enclose the ARB English Language Exemption Form with evidence

8. Available dates

We will endeavour to accommodate your wishes regarding the date of interview.

Please indicate below your preferred choice.

I would like to be offered the next available date

I would like to attend in _____ (specify month/s)

9. Comparative Matrix

You must enclose your Comparative Matrix stating where and how you believe your Supporting Material meets the criteria.

Please confirm whether you have followed the guidelines that indicate you should limit your Supporting Material submission to 60-80 pages of project work.

Please ensure that any essay or thesis submitted as evidence is accompanied by an executive summary of how the written work is relevant to the criteria.

The executive summaries will count towards the page count, but the written materials will not. The total volume of files submitted should not exceed 100MB.

Yes No

I have read and understood the above guidance on preparing my Supporting Material.

I understand that examiners have 90 minutes to review and assess my Comparative Matrix and Supporting Material prior to the examination day. I am aware that if my Supporting Material exceeds the limits advised, this may affect the outcome of my examination.

10. Checklist

Please note: incomplete applications are always returned and candidates are charged the appropriate scrutiny fee.

I enclose the following documents in support of my application:

Application form

Application fee of £1950.00

Curriculum vitae

IELTS Certificate or English Language Exemption Form

Original (or certified copies) of degree/diploma certificates

Original (or certified copies) of transcript/academic record

Passport-sized photograph

Copy of passport (the original must be presented for inspection on the day of your examination)

Cover sheet for Comparative Matrix to confirm number of words used. Please ensure this is signed and dated.

Comparative Matrix for Part 1, or Comparative Matrix for Part 2

References from past/present employers (where applicable)

Plagiarism report (if applicable)

10. Checklist I Continued

Deed poll or marriage certificate if the name on your certificates differs from the name you use now

Eligibility statement (where qualification is not strictly in architecture)

Statement from Registration or Professional body confirming access to the profession (where applicable)

Curriculum/Syllabus/Calendar of course (supply only sections relevant to you)

ARB Examination Application Declarations Document

11. Data protection

The Board can pass details of your examination result to the RIBA. Please tick the box if you would like this information to be disclosed.

12. Making your payment

1. By credit or debit card

We accept payment by MasterCard, Debit MasterCard, Visa Credit, Visa Debit, Visa Electron, Maestro and JCB cards only. We will call you at the telephone number given above in Section 2 to take payment.

Please note - Payment can only be made once an application form has been submitted.

2. Online banking

The details for paying by bank transfers are:

Account Name: Architects Registration Board

Bank Name: Natwest Plc

Sort Code: 60-09-15

Account Number: 36172618

Please ensure you state your full name as the reference.

For payments from overseas, you will need to use this code:

IBAN: GB33 NWBK 6009 1536 1726 18

SWIFT Code: NWBK GB2L

Please ensure that all additional costs (such as conversion and transfer fees) are for sender. Your application may be delayed if we do not receive the full amount due.

13. Equality and Diversity Data

In line with the Equality Act 2010, we are collecting this information to help us ensure that our policies and procedures do not act as a barrier to our services. It will also assist us in the continuous development of this and our other application processes.

Please be assured that the information you give will be held in the strictest confidence and held in accordance with data protection legislation.

Age	Under 18	51 - 65
	18 - 35	Over 65
	36 - 50	Prefer not to say

Ethnicity Please specify your ethnic origin. Ethnic categories are not about nationality, place of birth or citizenship. They are about the group to which you feel you belong to.

Asian or British Asian	Black or Black British
Bangladeshi	African
Chinese	Carribean
Indian	Any other Black background
Pakistani	
Any other Asian background	

White	Mixed
British	Asian and White
English	Black African and White
Irish	Black Carribean and White
Northern Irish	Any other mixed background
Scottish	
Welsh	
Any other White background	

Other

- Any other ethnic background
- Prefer not to say

Gender

Please specify your gender.

Female

Other

Male

Prefer not to say

Non-binary

Sexual orientation

Please specify your sexual orientation.

Heterosexual/Straight

Bisexual

Gay/Lesbian

Prefer not to say

Other

Religion

Buddhist

Hindu

Jewish

Other

Sikh

Non-religious

Christian

Prefer not to say

Muslim

Disability

Do you consider yourself to have a disability?

By disability, we mean any impairment that has a substantial and long-term effect on your ability to carry out normal day-to-day duties.

Yes

Prefer not to say

No

Socio-economic background

By the time you were 14 years old, had one or more of your parent(s) or guardian(s) completed a university degree course or equivalent (e.g. BA, BSc, or higher)?

Yes

Prefer not to say

No